

New stem-lepidosaurs from Vellberg, Germany: implications for
palaeoecology in the early diversification of Lepidosauromorpha

– Supplemental Material (Figures)

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SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 1

Supplementary Figure 1. Cranial elements of the referred material SMNS 91110-A of *Airistagiz segesi*, gen. et sp. nov. found as replicates of the holotype. A) segmented right frontal and its corresponding line drawing besides in

ventral (left) and dorsal (right) views; B) segmented postfrontal (above) and its corresponding line drawing (below) in dorsal view (anterior to the right); C) segmented postorbitals (above) and their corresponding line drawing (below) in right medial (left), right lateral (middle), and left lateral views (left); D) segmented left prefrontal and its corresponding line drawings besides in lateral (left) and medial views (right). Scale bars equal to 2mm (A, C right and middle) and 1mm (B, C left, D).

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 2

Supplementary Figure 2. Additional elements of the holotype material SMNS 91270 of *Hohlachia multidentis*, gen. et sp. nov. A) segmented epipterygoid; B) CT slide image of same (left) and its corresponding line drawing (right); C) segmented right humerus in ventral view (left) and its corresponding line drawing (right); D) same in lateral view (left) and its corresponding line drawing (right); E) segmented left humerus; F) segmented right ulna (left) and its corresponding line drawing (right) in anterior view; G) segmented right radius; H) segmented proximal end of an incomplete right femur. Scale bars equal to 2mm (A, B, H), 2.5mm (C, D), 1mm (E), 3mm (F, G).

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 3

Supplementary Figure 3. Bremer supports (cut 1) for the most parsimonious trees of the equal weights Parsimony analysis of the phylogenetic relationships of the new Vellberg lepidosauromorph taxa (in bold red). Numbers indicate number of extra steps necessary to collapse the corresponding branch.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 4

Supplementary Figure 4. Most parsimonious tree of the implied weighting Parsimony analysis ($k = 10, 12$) of the phylogenetic relationships of the new Vellberg lepidosauromorph taxa (in bold red). Note the empty lepidosaur-stem and the position of other early lepidosauromorph taxa (in bold).

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 5

Supplementary Figure 5. Strict consensus of 10 most parsimonious trees of the equal weighting Parsimony analysis of the new Vellberg lepidosauromorph taxa (in bold red) including *Elachistosuchus huenei* (in bold). Note the unorthodox position of *Youngina capensis*, some rhynchosaurs, and others.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 6

Supplementary Figure 6. Strict consensus of 2 most parsimonious trees of the implied weighting ($k = 10$) Parsimony analysis of the new Vellberg lepidosauromorph taxa (in bold red) including *Elachistosuchus huenei* (in bold). Note the empty lepidosaur-stem.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 7

Supplementary Figure 7. Maximum compatibility tree (halfcompat, 50% majority rule) resulting from the Bayesian analysis of the phylogenetic relationships of the new Vellberg lepidosauromorph taxa (in bold red). Numbers indicate the posterior probability of corresponding nodes different from 1.

